

Irregular migrant work in the national seafood processing policies in Morocco

Working Paper WP4 Morocco

Authors:

Hanane Darhour and Hajar Bouzid

Ibnou Zohr University, Faculty of Languages, Arts and Human Sciences
of Ait Melloul, Morocco

presidents and to all the people who contributed directly or indirectly to this research.
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About the DignityFIRM project

The DignityFIRM project is a Horizon Europe research project that is driven by the ambition to deepen the understanding of and to improve the policies related to irregular migrant work (IMW) in Farm to Fork (F2F) sectors. This report is part of WP4, which is aimed at understanding the governance arrangements underpinning the national policies addressing IMW in F2F sectors in five EU Member States (namely Germany, Italy, Poland, Spain and the Netherlands) and two Associated Countries (namely Morocco and Ukraine) in the period 2019-2024.

For more information about the project's research activities and deliverables, see <https://www.dignityfirm.eu>.

Abstract

This report is based on an analysis of the legislative dynamics in the seafood processing sector in Morocco, examining the main strategies and laws governing this economic sector, including the situation of undocumented foreign workers, who constitute a significant workforce, partially filling the local labor shortage. The analysis employs a qualitative methodology, drawing on a corpus of interviews conducted with various stakeholders, particularly professionals in the seafood processing sector, as well as a document review including reports and legal texts. The results show that the strategies governing this sector, especially the Halieutis strategy, focus primarily on adding value to fishery products, competitiveness, and the sustainability of resources for future generations. The issue of labor is addressed indirectly, through the promotion of the sector, which partly explains the absence of a specific policy concerning migrant workers in the Moroccan fishing industry. Added to this are the seasonality and structural fragility of the sector, which influence employment practices and conditions.

economy is not creating enough quality jobs for the rapidly growing working-age population and informality was considered a brake in the development of the industrial sectors, namely of fish processing sector. According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), the share of informal employment, which is defined as the proportion of workers without access to social security, may reach 60 to 80% in some sectors.

The issue of irregular migrants (IMs) is not an issue in the government's list of priorities, though it is locally managed and regionally governed among local government authorities in collaboration with civil society organizations, employers. Dakhla-Ouad Edahab for instance is one of the cities which has temporary detention centers for irregular migrants who come to cross to the Canary Islands as it is a border city to Mauritania. It also offers seasonal and day job opportunities for IMs who are willing to work and live in the city of Dakhla. The issue of migration and asylum is a priority issue in the Dakhla-Ouad Edahab region. This is due to its being a border region and the Kingdom's territorial connection to its African neighbors through the land and sea borders with Mauritania, a transit point for migrants heading to Morocco, or those using Morocco as a transit point towards European destinations. The fish processing sector has witnessed significant transformations, particularly in terms of its low-skilled labour force. Recently, in Dakhla the sector has become dependent on a mixed workforce, comprised of domestic as well as international migrant workers from sub-Saharan Africa, especially women. Many migrants work informally in the fish processing sector due to their irregular status. But they also occupy other jobs as observed by the coordinator of the Standing Committee for Protection and Monitoring in the Regional Commission for Human Rights in Dakhla: "migrants are now occupying numerous jobs, whether in the industrial sector, such as in fish freezing and canning units, or in the agricultural and rural pastoral estates, or in the service sector such as hotels, restaurants and shops, or in the construction sector, or in liberal professions. However, the number of those who have health insurance or a residence permit in a regular situation does not match the large number of them in the region's (Dakhla) jobmarket, which means that employers exploit the precariousness of their situation as irregular migrants to employ them as day laborers, without employment contracts".

In this context, Morocco initiated under His Majesty Mohammed VI's Royal grace collective campaigns, during 2013 and 2017, for the regularization of IMs. Labour market inclusion efforts for regularized migrants were put in place by the labour authority and the ANAPEC. However, and due to the Covid 19 and political crises that caused a disruption of the food supply chain across the global markets affected the enforcement of labour policies and employers' sanctions against the irregular employment of migrant workers. Irregular migrants living in Morocco and who still have the intention to cross to Europe can neither be deported back to their countries because of Morocco's alignment with the international conventions that forbid returning migrants and refugees in case of risk on their lives in their country.

4. Actors involved in the governance of the sector

The governance of the maritime fishing and seafood processing sector relies on the involvement of several institutional and professional actors. These actors participate, each at their own level, in the organization, regulation and operation of the sector. The Department of Maritime Fisheries, attached to the Ministry of Agriculture and Maritime Fisheries, plays a central role in this governance. It is responsible for defining the sector's general guidelines, implementing public policies, particularly the Halieutis strategy, and ensuring compliance with regulations concerning fishing, processing, and marketing of seafood products.

Through its actions, this department directly influences the organization of the sector and impacts production conditions, as well as, indirectly, working conditions. Beside the Ministry of Agriculture and Maritime Fisheries, the Federation of Industries for the Processing and Valorization of Fisheries Products (FENIP) is an important actor in the sector. FENIP is a professional organization created on November 21, 1996. It encompasses more than 300 seafood processing and valorization companies operating in the branches of activity of the sector. The fishmeal and oil industry is represented by the National Association of Manufacturers of Fish Meal and Oil (ANAFAP); ground freezing of seafood is represented by National Association of Seafood Freezing Industries (ANICOM); the seafood processing industries is represented by FIPROMER; the fish canning industry is represented by UNICOP; and the aquaculture sector is represented by the National Union of Aqua-culturists of

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ABOUT DignityFIRM

Towards becoming sustainable and resilient societies we must address the structural contradictions between our societies' exclusion of migrant workers and their substantive role in producing our food.

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